

SIGNIFICANCE OF MULTIPLE PATHWAYS IN ADAPTATION. PART I.
INHIBITION OF SPORULATION OF *ASPERGILLUS NIGER* AS INDUCED
BY EXPOSURE TO TRIPHENYLMETHANE DYES

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Normally the spores of a given strain of *A. niger* take nearly 35 hours for sporulation, the period of which is progressively delayed by increased doses of exposure to methyl violet. This delaying effect finally attains a constant value, independent of the duration of exposure. The pattern of inhibition of sporulation, as induced by methyl violet, is the same as by the two other triphenylmethane dyes.

A vital cell process like sporulation may have multiple pathways for adaptation in response to a stimulus.

The phenomenon of adaptation has been accounted for by two major classes of hypotheses— one class involving the assumption that individuals themselves are the primary seat of direct adaptive changes and the other, involving the assumption that individuals of all possible properties do exist in an apparently homogeneous culture. The former operates by actual modification of cells and the latter by selection (Laser, *Biochem. J.*, 1952, 51, 57; Eddy, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1954, B142, 267; Stanier, *Ann. Rev. Microbiol.*, 1951, 5, 35). The present communication is restricted to a study of the first of the two hypotheses.

The direct adaptive changes of cells, initiated by a given stimulus and very often lost on its withdrawal (as opposed to mutation), are supposed to be due to potentialities or intrinsic virtues rather than newly developed properties of an organism to fight or to adjust itself to a changed environment; these virtues are, as a matter of fact, originally present in the organism in the form of multiple metabolic routes for a given biochemical performance. Instances of multiple pathways for a given biochemical function are not rare. Triple pathways (Lipman, *Nature*, 1936, 138, 588; Dickens, *ibid.*, p. 1057) of glucose oxidation may be cited as an instance. However, the above assumption to account for adaptation demands that each of the metabolic reactions, particularly those relating to vital cell processes viz., germination, sporulation, respiration etc., must have multiple routes in one and the same organism (Bose, *Science & Culture*, 1955, 21, 168).

The present work has therefore been undertaken to study whether or not multiple pathways to account for adaptation are involved in the sporulation of a given strain of *A. niger*.

EXPERIMENTAL

Organism and Media.—The organism used in these experiments was a strain of *A. niger* G₂Br. It was maintained on an agar medium consisting of glucose (50.0 g.),

sodium nitrate (2.0 g.), potassium dihydrogen phosphate (1.0 g.), magnesium sulphate (0.5 g.), yeast extract (0.5 g.), malt extract (0.5 g.) and potato extract (hot water extract of 100 g. of potatoes per litre).

The medium used for experimental work, viz., harvesting of spores, determining the period of sporulation etc., was the same as the maintenance medium.

Method of obtaining conidium suspension free from vegetative growth, technique of exposure to dyes, etc. were detailed in an earlier publication (Mazumdar and Bose, *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1955, 18, 11). A spore suspension was freed from vegetative growth by filtration through wet cotton wool. In exposing these spores they were suspended in a concentration of 10^7 per c.c. in an 1% aqueous solution of triphenylmethane dyes, viz., methyl violet, crystal violet and malachite green.

Method of determining the Period of Sporulation.—The spores freed from vegetative growth were inoculated into a molten agar medium and then 2 to 3 drops of the inoculated medium were uniformly smeared with the help of a loop handle on the surface of a microscopic slide, placed on a wet cotton pad, kept inside a sterile petri dish; and the whole was placed in an incubator at 30°. A series of petri dishes were similarly treated for the purpose. It should be noted here that the number of spores in a smear preparation was adjusted to be very small, otherwise luxuriant growth of mycelial threads would make observation difficult.

After regular intervals microscopic slides, so incubated, were taken out and observed under a microscope using lactophenol as the mounting fluid. In practice, the time-interval between inoculation and formation of the first conidium was taken as the period of sporulation.

The size of spore-head being larger, it was not possible to determine in a given smear preparation the percentage of spores sporulating at different periods of incubation. The time of sporulation of as many as five different spores in any preparation was therefore determined.

The period of sporulation of exposed spores was similarly determined. In practice, treated spores after a given period of exposure were washed several times aseptically till the washing liquid became colorless. It was, however, observed that dyes, not mechanically adhering to the surface of spores but physically adsorbed on them, could not be removed. The spores, thus washed free of dyes, were treated in the same way as referred to above for determining the period of sporulation.

Period of Sporulation at Different Levels of Exposure to Methyl Violet.—The sporulating period is normally different with different spores (Table Ia). It may vary from 32.5 to 38.0 hours. This difference in absence of any treatment may be regarded as individual variation. Previous exposure to methyl violet tends to inhibit sporulation so much that it may now take more time than what is normally required. To ascertain the significance of this observed inhibition, the data were subjected to 'F' test by statistical methods (Table Ib).

The high value of 'F', as shown in Table Ib, clearly indicates that all the treatments are significant, whereas the data due to replications are not significantly different. Comparing the difference between the means for the blank and treatments with the

critical difference at 5% (2.79) and 1% (3.85) levels, it is found that all exposures are significant at both the levels; exposure for 3 days is not significantly effective when compared with 1 day's exposure. Exposures for 3, 5 and 7 days have the highest inhibiting effect, but amongst themselves they do not vary significantly. It can therefore be concluded from statistical analysis that the maximum inhibiting effect is observed up to 5 days' exposure and beyond this, the effect is not significant.

TABLE IA

Effect of exposure to methyl violet on the period of sporulation.

Individual spore.	0 days.	Period of sporulation after exposure for			
		1 day.	3 days.	5 days.	7 days.
1	33.0 hrs.	41.0 hrs.	46.0 hrs.	44.5 hrs.	47.0 hrs.
2	37.0	39.0	44.0	42.0	43.5
3	36.0	43.5	43.5	43.0	46.0
4	33.0	42.5	42.5	47.0	45.0
5	36.0	39.0	41.5	46.0	41.0
Mean	35.0	41.0	43.5	44.5	44.5

TABLE IB

Analysis of variance (methyl violet).

Sources of error.	D. F.	S. S.	M. S.	F.	Significance.
Replications	4	11.50	2.875	..	
Treatments	4	311.50	80.375	18.50	Significant
Error	16	69.50	4.344		
Total	24	402.50			

Pattern of Inhibition induced in Sporulation by Triphenylmethane Dyes.—The effect of exposure to crystal violet and malachite green on sporulation was studied (Tables IIA and IIIA) and the data were subjected to statistical analysis (Tables IIB and IIIB). It appears that crystal violet and malachite green also exert delaying action on sporulation. The statistical analysis of the data clearly points out that all the treatments are significant, not only with respect to control but also amongst themselves except after 5 days' exposure, beyond which almost a constant value is attained. Thus, the pattern of inhibition induced is the same as in the case of methyl violet.

TABLE IIA

Effect of exposure to crystal violet on the period of sporulation.

Individual spore.	0 day.	Sporulating period after exposure for				9 days.
		1 day.	3 days.	5 days.	7 days.	
1	32.5 hrs.	42.0 hrs.	43.0 hrs.	47.0 hrs.	45.0 hrs.	47.5 hrs.
2	37.5	44.0	41.0	42.0	41.0	44.0
3	36.0	39.0	46.5	44.5	48.5	42.0
4	34.0	45.0	46.0	43.0	46.0	45.5
5	35.0	40.0	41.0	46.0	42.5	46.0
Mean	35.0	42.0	43.5	44.5	45.0	45.0

TABLE IIB.

Analysis of variance (crystal violet).

Sources of error.	D. F.	S. S.	M. S.	F.	Significance.
Replications	4	9.83	2.46	...	
Treatments	5	370.00	74.00	12.65	Significant
Error	20	116.67	5.83	...	
Total	29	496.50	...		

TABLE IIIA

Effect of malachite green on the period of sporulation.

Individual spore.	Sporulating period after exposure for				
	0 day.	1 day.	3 days.	5 days.	7 days.
1	34.5 hrs	47.0 hrs.	43.5 hrs.	50.5 hrs.	45.0 hrs.
2	32.5	46.5	49.0	49.0	48.0
3	38.0	42.0	44.5	48.0	45.5
4	34.0	44.0	47.5	47.0	50.0
5	36.0	43.0	48.0	45.5	50.5
Mean	35.0	44.5	46.5	48.0	48.0

TABLE IIIB

Analysis of variance (malachite green).

Sources of error.	D. F.	S. S.	M. S.	F.	Significance.
Replications	4	5.3	1.3	...	
Treatments	4	593.5	148.3	26.9	Significant
Error	16	88.7	5.5	...	
Total	25	687.5	...		

C O N C L U S I O N

Normally the spores of the given strain of *A. niger* take 35 hours to sporulation. Data obtained show that previous exposure to methyl violet delays normal sporulation. This progressively increased delay, which attains a constant value, may indicate that more than one biochemical paths are involved in sporulation and that at least one of these paths is probably sensitive to the action of the dye. Inhibition studies, as conducted with the two other triphenylmethane dyes, also indicate the same pattern of inhibition, which implies that more than one biochemical paths may be involved in the process.

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